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Problems of Preventing Deviant Behavior of Students in the Extreme Conditions of the Coronavirus Pandemic

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Abstract

The issue of legal protection of minors appears to be the most important one, being of particular relevance due to insufficient elaboration of the problem under consideration in modern socio-economic realities. The problem of preventing deviant behavior of students in the extreme conditions of the coronavirus pandemic and uncoordinated public manifestations of young people is one of the most relevant in pedagogy, criminology and sociology, since, firstly, it poses a danger to society. Secondly, deviant behavior is prone to organizing new offenses and involving other minors. The fact that in case of deviant behavior, the situation according to which the indicators of deviance become the higher, the higher is the degree of danger of illegal acts remains unchanged represents a particular danger.

In this regard, the purpose of this article is to formulate and theoretically substantiate modern forms of prevention of deviant behavior of schoolchildren in the extreme conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The leading approach to the study of this problem is the dialectical method of cognition based on the use of dialectical materialistic teaching.

The article studies the problems of preventing deviant, delinquent and addictive behavior of students in the extreme conditions of the coronavirus pandemic, taking into account the latest changes and additions to the current legislation; the author's judgments on the stated problem are presented. As a result of the study, the necessity of an early resolution of the crisis component of measures to counteract the deviant behavior of underage students is substantiated.

The practical significance of the obtained research results lies in the fact that the materials presented in the article can be used by teachers of secondary educational institutions, teachers of pedagogical and legal universities, judges and law enforcement officers in the implementation of professional activities to prevent deviant behavior of students.

In the final part, the conclusions of the article are given, clearly revealing those aspects that are briefly stated in the abstract.

The research methods are general scientific methods of cognition (formal-logical, systemic); special (comparative legal, etc.), theoretical (analysis; synthesis; generalization); empirical (study of normative, scientific and educational literature).

The empirical base of the study includes scientific literature, textbooks, teaching aids on pedagogical disciplines and criminology in the field of deviant topics, addictive behavior in children, the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, normative documents regulating the liability of juvenile offenders.

Keywords: prevention, crime, deviation, family, minors, children, coronavirus.

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Introduction

According to the UN International Convention on the Rights of the Child (New York, November 20, 1989) (Soviet Journal of International Law, Russia, 1991), Resolution of the Government of the Russian Federation of August 23, 1993 No. 848 “On the Implementation of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and the World declarations on ensuring the survival, protection and development of children” (Collection of acts of the President and the Government of the Russian Federation, 1993) and in accordance with Art. 38 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, motherhood and childhood, the family are under the protection of the state. The issue of legal protection of minors in the Russian state appears to be the most important one, being of particular relevance due to insufficient elaboration of the problem under consideration at present which is of great importance in modern socio-economic realities.

Recently, the number of socially disadvantaged families has increased in Russia. These include: families with limited social resources, with a disturbed structure, with deviant and addictive behavior, pedagogically incompetent ones.

The problem of preventing deviant behavior of students in the extreme conditions of the pandemic of the new coronavirus infection COVID-19 (some students, mainly foreigners, have been transferred to distance learning in the Russian Federation due to the spread of coronavirus infection and the need to protect the life and health of citizens) has become relevant. Following the world events connected with the spread of the new coronavirus infection COVID-19, numerous changes are being made to the legislation of the Russian Federation. As a result of the adoption of the Decree of the President of the Russian Federation of March 25, 2020 No. 206 "On the announcement of non-working days in the Russian Federation" (Official Internet portal of legal information, 2020), all spheres of society were affected, including the spheres of criminal law and education of the Russian Federation. As a result of the sudden outbreak of the spread of the COVID-19 viral infection, the prolonged use of distance technologies in the field of education without preliminary preparation for this can affect the quality of modern education in the Russian Federation and, as a result, lead to an increase in the cases of deviant behavior of students) and inconsistent public manifestations of youth.

This is one of the most relevant issues in pedagogy, criminology and sociology, since, firstly, it poses a danger to society and acquires particular relevance in the light of the changes made to Art. 110, 116 and 116.1 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation in terms of regulating liability for battery and other violent acts that caused physical pain and additions to the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation by Articles 110.1, 110.2.

In connection with the introduction of distance learning in the country, studying youth, including children, received practically unlimited access to Internet resources in those volumes and for such an amount of time that had been previously inaccessible to them.

The problem is that on the Internet, schoolchildren and students can not only search for educational information, but also violate public order, laws and other regulatory legal acts; in particular, young people can get access to legally protected computer information. It is, as a rule, the information about persons, objects, facts, events, phenomena and processes that are protected by law. Article 272 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation of June 13, 1996 No. 63-FL "Illegal access to computer information" provides for criminal liability for unlawful access to legally protected computer information if this act entailed the destruction, blocking, modification or copying of computer information. Persons who have reached the age of sixteen must carry such a responsibility.

The scientific novelty of the work lies in the fact that it is an up-to-date study of the problems of preventing deviant, delinquent and addictive behavior of students in the extreme conditions of the coronavirus pandemic, taking into account the latest changes and additions to the current legislation. On the basis of the study, the need to constantly modernize the already existing methods of prevention, countermeasures is substantiated, taking into account modern trends, newly emerging causes and conditions of deviant behavior of minors.

The validity and reliability of the research results and conclusions are based on the analysis of domestic regulatory material and the works of Russian and foreign authors. The work makes a new contribution to the development of legal education.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to characterize the deviant, delinquent and addictive behavior of adolescents at school; search for new approaches of solving the problems of children's deviations; formulation and theoretical substantiation of modern forms of prevention of deviant behavior in a child's environment.

Literature review

According to Rogova, deviant behavior as a socio-criminological phenomenon is accompanied by socio-psychological maladjustment (2019) of the personality itself is characterized by a stable antisocial orientation, increased aggressiveness, and it is prone to organizing new offenses and involving other minors. According to Zotov, the fact that with all the mobility and dynamism of deviant behavior, the state, when the indicators of deviance become the higher, the higher the degree of danger of committed illegal acts remains unchanged represents a particular danger (2015, p.73).

Deviant behavior of a minor can lead to deformation of the personality, to the features of which Antonyan attributes the beginning of illegal activities, low level of education and culture, absence or loss of family relations, base (immoral) personality traits (deformation of moral consciousness), lack of positive incentives to work and social duty (2012, p.241).

The World Health Organization (WHO) distinguishes between primary, secondary and tertiary prevention.

Schneider defines primary prevention as a complex of preventive measures, mass and universal prevention of actions that deviate from social norms, carried out more often among children and adolescents in order to prevent deviant behavior (2005, p.20).

Secondary prevention of deviant behavior involves the task of early detection of neuropsychiatric disorders, rehabilitation, correction of unfavorable individual and social factors that are likely to cause deviant behavior and work.

Tertiary prevention is focused on persons who have already developed deviant behavior, i.e., on the prevention of recurrence of harmful consequences for the individual and society. In fact, as Rogova notes, this is a modification intervention, or an active impact on an even narrower circle of people with stable or highly probable behavioral deviations (2019, p.5).

Kleiberg notes that the prevention of deviant behavior involves the implementation of certain principles (2001).

The work of Zautorova (2018) is devoted to the correction of deviant behavior of children, the emergence of new types of "delinquent behavior" of minors is distinguished by Borodina, Mushkina and Sadilova (2014), such psychologists as Ovsyannikova, Rakhmanina and Taisaeva also note a number of psychological deviations in adolescents (2019, p.51).

Prevention of delinquency assumes that the school becomes a place where the child actually finds use of his capabilities. Prevention based on work in schools presupposes, according to Rogova, the creation of a network of "healthy schools", the inclusion of preventive classes in the curricula of all schools (2019, p.12–13).

As individual studies show, and according Gorkovaya, a different vision of specialists in different areas of prevention of "a portrait of children and adolescents with illegal behavior" is one of the significant reasons for the insufficient effectiveness of preventive measures; "which complicates the interaction between them in solving a common problem" (2020).

Goneev, Lifintseva and Yalpaeva distinguish the following methods aimed at correcting deviant personality behavior: 1) destruction of the negative type of character and the method of character reconstruction. 2) restructuring of the motivational sphere and self-awareness: objective rethinking of one's advantages and disadvantages; reorientation of self-awareness; persuasion; prognosis of negative behavior; 3) restructuring of life experience: prescription; restriction; retraining; shifting; regulation of lifestyle; 4) prevention of negative and stimulation of positive behavior: encouragement and punishment; competition; positive perspective (2011, p.133–175).

The concept of delinquency was introduced into science in the 1950s by Kohen. He defined it as adolescent's antisocial illegal behavior, embodied in his actions (actions or inaction) that harm both individual citizens and society as a whole (Kohen, 1955).

Methodology

The methodological basis of the study was made up of the dialectical method of cognition, as well as the following general scientific (formal-logical, systemic, systemic-structural) and special (comparative legal, etc.), theoretical (analysis, synthesis, generalization); statistical methods of cognition.

During the research, the following methods were used: theoretical (analysis; synthesis; generalization); empirical (study of normative, scientific and educational literature).

Results

Social tension in the country gives rise to a serious increase in various kinds of violations of social norms by minors: the scale of offenses and crimes, adolescent alcoholism, crimes related to drug trafficking and other manifestations of deviant behavior are constantly increasing. This type of deviation is taking on the character of an epidemic.

In just one year in Russia, every twentieth crime was committed by minors or with their complicity. On average, 54369 juveniles who have committed crimes are identified per year.

Economic instability is closely related to social tensions. Lack of funds, high food prices, rising unemployment make it difficult for minors to find work, cause unrest in society, distrust of government authorities, in the most acute situations can lead adolescents to openly express their dissatisfaction with them by participating in uncoordinated protest rallies, meetings, demonstrations, processions and picketing. Social "heat" of this nature is causing the growth of child crime. Minors are more sensitive to such disasters. And due to insufficient life experience, increased emotionality, minors in most cases misunderstand the reasons for what is happening, which leads to a more rapid reaction in the form of deviant behavior. At present, due to the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdowns, one can state the onset of an economic crisis, which is undoubtedly reflected in the statistical indicators of the juvenile delinquency rate, which peaked in 2008 (the number of children who committed crimes amounted to 107.8 thousand, in 2012–2014 – 54-59 thousand) (according to the statistics of the Unified Interdepartmental Information and Statistical System (UIISS)).

Juvenile delinquency is a dynamically developing phenomenon. In this regard, it is necessary to constantly modernize countermeasures, taking into account modern trends, newly emerging causes and conditions of deviant behavior of minors. With the aggravation of military conflicts in different parts of the world, teenagers become participants in hostilities and war crimes. Teenagers participate in paramilitary groups of political organizations of extremists, in racketeering, cooperate with the mafia, engage in prostitution and pimping, and commit economic crimes.

To prevent socially dangerous behavior of minors and young people during distance learning in time of the pandemic, first of all, it is necessary to anticipate the socially dangerous behavior of minors studying on the Internet, as well as to take a number of preventive measures to prevent children and young people from accessing information protected by law located in external media, in a computer memory or a computer network, it is necessary to strengthen control over the use of computers by them, for which the developed computer programs can help.

Deviant behavior (from Latin – deviation) is not consistent with the current rules, laws and attitudes of society, stable, regularly and persistently, consciously repeated (multiple or prolonged) any antisocial (abnormal) action of a person (system of actions), deviating in its motives, value orientations and results from the generally accepted, most widespread and well-established cultural values, ideals and social standards in a given society, from social, important socio-psychological and moral group norms for its motives, value orientations and results, whether they are the norms of mental health (providing for the presence of explicit and hidden psychopathology), rights, morals that violate socially approved norms and contradict the accepted rules of human community, activities, customs, traditions, as well as negative (for example, drug use, alcoholism, aggression, gambling), socially neutral (for example, begging), anti-disciplinary behavior that does not correspond to generally accepted or officially established social norms (which may change), not satisfying the social expectations of society in a specific period of time, considered by most of the members of society according to the theory of anomie (a state of lawlessness) as reprehensible and unacceptable; significantly different from harmony and diverse in structure, types and forms; characterized by mandatory censure from the public, negative assessments from other people, violation of the process of acquisition, as well as reproduction of social norms, a specific way of changing expectations by demonstrating a value attitude to them, manifested in: a) causing real damage to society – public well-being or people around them - or b) causing damage to oneself, as well as accompanied by socio-psychological absence of adaptation of the personality itself. Negative deviant behavior destroys social relations, leads to biological, genetic and social degradation of the individual, causes problems in the socialization of the younger generation.

Depending on the level of harm caused to the interests of society, a group or an individual, several types (groups) of deviant behavior are distinguished:

1. Destructive (auto-destructive (self-destructive)) behavior –this is behavior that deviates from medical and psychological norms, which threatens the integrity and development of the personality itself, causing significant damage only to the personality itself (intra-destructive – suicidal (suicidal attempts), conformist, narcissistic, food addiction, chemical dependence (substance abuse), fanatical behavior (for example, involvement in a destructive religious cult), autistic behavior, victim behavior (victim behavior), activities with a pronounced risk to life) and not corresponding to generally accepted social and moral norms-hoarding, conformism, masochism, etc.

Externally destructive behavior is addictive, antisocial, non-standard behavior, actions that go beyond social stereotypes.

2. Antisocial (illegal delinquent) behavior – behavior that is a violation in communication, in training, in self-awareness of both moral and legal norms, contradicting legal norms and threatening the social order and well-being of others and expressed in petty hooliganism, robberies, murders and other crimes: violence against younger and weaker peers, animals; battery, arson, sadistic actions, petty theft (for example, deliberate regular stealing of money by a child from parents), vandalism; damage to other people's property; distribution and drug sales.

3. Asocial (immoral) behavior – this is evasion from fulfilling the moral norms accepted in society, which directly threatens the well-being of interpersonal relations (manifestation in behavior: leaving home; deviation from study; systematic absences from school; aggressive behavior; insults, demonstrations, defiance, involvement in gambling for money, vagrancy, dependency, lies; extortion, sexual deviations – promiscuous sexual relations, wall inscriptions and drawings of an obscene nature, profanity); causing harm to the individual and social communities (family, friends, neighbors or surrounding people), manifested in drunkenness, alcoholism and early alcoholism, early drug addiction; suicide attempts, etc., violating some social, cultural and especially legal norms.

Addictive behavior (from the English word addiction) of children is one of the types of deviant (deviant) behavior; one of the special forms of specific activity or destructive (externally destructive) behavior.

According to the results of the studies, minors from 11 to 17 years old are under the influence of addictions most often. Various intoxicants have been tried by 85% of adolescents at least once.

Deviant auto-aggressive behavior of adolescents can be illegal, antisocial, anti-disciplinary, auto-aggressive (self-harm, thoughts of suicide), delinquent (from Latin *delictum* – misdemeanor, English – delinquency – offense, offense).

Discussion

After analyzing the works of researchers Antonyan and others (2012), the reasons for juvenile delinquency were summarized.

Of all juvenile delinquents aged 16-17, 30% did not work and did not study, 40% of murderers, 37.9% of those who committed robberies).

The representatives of psychological schools distinguish the following factors (psychoanalysis – unconscious motives of deviation, psychological characteristics of the deviant's personality (Freud, 1994, p.29–34); neo-Freudianism – a lack of emotional contact with the mother (Horney, 1994; Bowlby, 2003); lack of a sense of security in the first years of life (Erickson, 1993); family structure and type of upbringing (Adler, 1998); behaviorism – distortion of the socialization process, abuse of punishment, cruel attitude towards children (Bandura, 1961, p.575–582; Beron (1997); psychodidactic direction – the role of educational failures of a child in the development of deviations (Nichishina, 2018, p.10–11) and others.

As a result of the use of psychoactive substances, physical, social, psychological damage occurs (Krylova, 2013).

In Russian psychology in the works of Bratusya the problem of norm-pathology is presented (1988). Nevsky identifies the following stages in the development of asocial behavior: - unacceptable behavior (episodic pranks, mischief); - censured behavior (associated with more systematic condemnation by educators); - deviant behavior (morally negative manifestations and misconduct); - delinquent (pre-criminal) behavior; - criminal behavior; - destructive behavior (1983).

A teenager with deviant behavior has his own characteristics and characteristic personality traits that contribute to the emergence of addiction, which are indicated by a number of authors (Krylova, 2013; Kleyberg, 2001; Kolesov, 1984; Pirozhkov, 1995; Rudensky, 2019; Feldshtein, 2012): negative mental tension; reduced tolerance of difficulties; accentuated willingness to take risks; hidden inferiority complex; mental rigidity; stereotypicality, pronounced orientation towards the norms of the deviant adolescent group; repetitive behavior; anxiety, unpredictability of behavior; high aggressiveness.

Conclusion

The consistently high rates of neglect and homelessness, alcoholism, drug addiction among adolescents make one think about the need for changes in the complex of measures to prevent deviant behavior of minors. To highlight effective measures for the prevention of unlawful acts of minors and analyze current problems and development trends in the field of combating deviant behavior of teenage students, it is necessary to determine the theoretical base, the basis of which is the concept of “juvenile delinquency”. Concluding the study devoted to the consideration of the prevention of deviant behavior of underage students, it is definitely possible to draw conclusions about the need to resolve the crisis component of measures to counteract the deviant behavior of underage students as soon as possible.

Among the problems of social and economic recovery, an important place is occupied by the creation of a fundamentally new model of the state system of social prevention of deviant behavior of minors.

At the same time in the realities of our modern state, it is unrealistic to talk about the creation of a completely new service, especially in the context of today's worsening economic situation amid coronavirus infection.

Legal protection of minors implies the need to identify circumstances related to the living conditions and upbringing of each minor, his state of health, other factual data, as well as the reasons for committing deviant acts, in order to take measures provided for by law to achieve the maximum educational impact of the educational process in relation to deviant students minors.

The problem of deviant behavior of underage students requires further in-depth analysis, since their antisocial behavior is dangerous not only for society, but also for themselves, because it forms the wrong worldview and habits. Therefore, it is so important to constantly study this topic, subject it to analysis and develop new methods of struggle, constantly modernize existing methods of prevention, countermeasures, taking into account modern trends, newly emerging causes and conditions of deviant behavior of children. The process of education remains dominant in the system of prevention of juvenile delinquency.

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